

Marital Relationship and the Woman's Thirst for Freedom in the Day in Shadow by Nayantara Sahgal

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Abstract

Nayantara Sahgal is a socio- political novelist. She gives great social awareness of contemporary sensibilities in her novels like movement of social forces, memories of the colonial past and its impact on the people. She explores the collective dreams of the Indian people through her novels as an angry Gandhian of early generation of post-colonial India. The novel, The Day in Shadow, is set in Delhi and close to the seat of power and justice. The novel also revolves around a female Protagonist Simrit who believes ardently in the concept of freedom and is refused to take decision individually. The other characters are the vibrant in the novel. The Day in Shadow gives a sensitive account of the suffering of a woman in Indian society when she opts to dissolve a seventeen year old marriage. A divorced woman is stigmatized forever and she is curiously watched by others.

Keywords : Post colonial, Post Independent, feminism, Patriarchy.

The Day in Shadow is the story of Som and Simrit and it begins at a point where divorce between the husband and the wife has already taken place and the seventeen year old marital bond is already dissolved. Through the technique of flashback and reminiscences, the reader is allowed to have a plunge into the world of Som and Simrit where the factors like understanding, sympathy and compassion are missing. Right from the beginning, Simrit's selection of Som as a husband was not a result of any deep thought. She was simply attracted by the flash, the glitter, colour and enthusiasm which were the hallmarks of Som's personality. Simrit's Brahmin parents as well as her friends disapproved of Som. But Simrit, ignoring the warnings of her parents and friends, decides to marry Som:

Her Brahmin parents with their instinctive withdrawal from anything outside the fold had been frankly upset at her choice of a businessman husband, but her friends had not liked him either. They had thought him a boor. People always disliked and distrusted commercial flash and flair if they did not possess it themselves (The Day in Shadow 9)

Som wants to become a popular and successful man in the society. So he works towards them. Simrit is fascinated by Som's flash. She sees this aspect of Som as capable of filling the void of her "solitary,

book loving childhood” (4). Their marriage could end for seventeen long years because the relationship works smoothly on the surface level. Neither Som nor Simrit try to care the deeper layers of relationship. It is like “a game of its own in which intensity depth and devotion were never brought into play at all” (4). Conflict or final breakage of relationship, lack of partnership and sharing spirit between the husband and wife are enlisted by Nayantara Sahgal in this novel. And sadly enough, these are missing in Som- Simrit relationship.

Simrit is dominated and expected to play a meek role. Simrit who is essentially traditional in nature, never nurture any desire to have an edge over Som. She only wants to ‘be’, to realise herself as a living, feeling human being, tender and energetic with life and action. She likes to take own decisions. But being practical and optimistic in outlook, she never questions Som’s authority in the greater, wider interest of having pleasant relationship with Som. She preferred not to affirm herself, because doing so will mean “a battle - and she had never been prepared to fight” (4). Her optimistic can be seen unity.

Simrit shares her experience about the world with Som kindly. Som expects her to confirm to the ideal of submissive womanhood and considers the discrimination of their relationship as the right order of things. Simrit is denied to have freedom. She does not have rights to take decisions of everyday life, not even in the choice of curtains or chair covers. “Even there Som had a veto. Not even about servants. She had dismissed the cook twice for drunkenness and bad behavior and Som had kept him on” (38). Overall plight, pain and deep discontent culminate her for divorce. Simrit’s desire to ‘be’ is expressed by Nayantara Sahgal thus: “She wondered if she could be like that ever again, look ahead, make decision, actively be, instead of just getting past each day, feeling as if large pieces of her had been cut out with scissors, with an icy wind blowing through the gaps” (16).

Som believes that a woman is to beget the children, look after her children, husband and home. Simrit uses the opportunity tactfully to convey her feelings and beliefs to Som through Vetter. But she feels so turbulent. Moreover, Som has faith in Vetter and his intervention in this matter may have influenced Som. But Simrit is not an opportunist or otherwise a tactful person. She is genuine and pure at heart. She is beyond such pretensions. She is not elegant enough to turn things to her benefit. Moreover, the acute suffering snowed under her mind to such an extent. She cannot think systematically and logically in this way. The result is that both Som and Simrit remain at bay from each other. They have gap between them widened day by day because of the absence of contact between them. Both Simrit and Som are to be blamed for that. Simrit has never opened her heart to pass on Som of the volcano of feelings bump in her mind day by day.

Raj proves to be a very good friend to Simrit. After having considerate and understanding relationship with Raj Simrit marries Raj. The new marriage relationship between Simrit and Raj gives heavy attack to Som. Nayantara Sahgal reacts sharply when an interviewer remarked that Simrit’s break-up with Som turns out to be a joke towards the end when she accepts Raj as her man and thereby losing reader’s sympathy and admiration:

No., I certainly do not agree with this explanation. Perhaps you get baffled when Simrit finds happiness with a man, may be because you are an orthodox male who resents such a development in a woman’s life. I personally do not believe a woman has to be a martyr to prove her goodness (20).

Simrit is a subservient follower of Raj after marriage. Raj gives equal preference to Simrit to take decision in her life. For instance Simrit turns down Raj’s proposal to have dinner in a hotel and “Raj accepted defeat” (14). Later Raj’s proposal to have a coffee at a restaurant is turned down and she suggests instead of restaurant they shall go home and have coffee there. Raj says: “All right, let’s go. With you I face a dead end at every turn, unlike Som who must have ridden roughshod and triumphant, didn’t he?” (157). Apart from these matters of lighter vein, even in

serious issues, Simrit doesn't blindly listen to Raj. She decides to meet Som's company lawyer Moolchand against his [Raj's] wishes. Even Raj recognizes her independent spirit: "Her new life had nothing to do with him or any man... She didn't need a man for identity or status" (139).

Raj had claimed to recover Simrit for his own sake. Simrit fails to understand Raj's biased nature. She blindly pays divine respect to him and feels lively in his company: A smile from him, as N. Shamota says "radiated an atmosphere of suppressed jubilation that lapped around her in waves". (Shamota 106-107)

Sahgal opposes and rejects in tradition Manu's idea of an ideal wife, the idea of a virtuous woman through Simrit, one can see oppression of women in the name of religion, the passivity of Hinduism and social injustice sanctioned by religion. What she values in traditional is compassion, charity, love, preaching of non-violence, values like courage strength, single-minded endeavour, a tendency for non-material etc., She rejects materialism, violence, corruption, etc in modernity. She accepts and appreciates autonomous of individual, freedom, including sexual freedom to women, equal rights for women, the utility and significance of communication and direct approach in the modern concept.

Simrit's life reflects the crisis of contemporary and traditional India society. It affects not only women but also men. Sahgal portrays Not only women are suffering on account of the system of patriarchy even men are affected adversely in this novel. Som is also a sufferer of the patriarchal system. He is a loser. He loses love and family. He fails to see that women are trying to change the existing world order. Here, is place for sincerity, pretence and dual morality.

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